

The Impact of Streetscapes on Real Estate Prices: A Case Study of Onomichi, Japan

Hiroki Baba ¹

¹ Affiliation: School of Science and Engineering, Chuo University, Tokyo, Japan

Correspondence: Hiroki Baba (hbaba893@g.chuo-u.ac.jp)

Submission Type. Poster.

BoK Concepts. [GS2] Economic aspects, [CV1] History and trends, [GD2] Data Collection

Keywords. real estate, housing, low-priced properties, historical assets, Japan

1 Introduction

The price of real estate transactions serves as an indicator of a city's perceived attractiveness. Nevertheless, the determination of real estate prices is a multifaceted process influenced by a variety of factors, including the characteristics of the property itself and its surrounding environment (Kim et al., 2017). In particular, roads utilized in daily life have been shown to be correlated with real estate prices. For instance, Shimizu (2014) reported a positive correlation between real estate prices and the width of road frontage. Wang and Rasouli (2022) examined the impact of streetscape features on lodging prices in Amsterdam and found that greening increases prices, while a pedestrian-friendly environment decreases them. Thus, although streets can affect real estate pricing in many ways, research in this area has been limited. Landscape elements are inherently constructed throughout the region, so it is imperative to analyze the contribution of streetscapes to real estate on a broader scale.

This study examines whether real estate prices are affected by broader streetscapes. Specifically, I create typologies capturing district-level streetscapes in terms of street configuration and examine their correlation with real estate prices. The study area is a scenic district in Onomichi, Japan. This district is adjacent to the Inland Sea, with residential areas located on the slopes. Its view of the Seto Inland Sea, coupled with the presence of

numerous temples and shrines, makes it one of Japan's premier tourist destinations, rendering it an ideal site for this study.

2 Data and Method

2.1 Data and Software Availability

The data were obtained from the Real Estate Information Library, operated by the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (MLIT), which include transaction prices of residential land and buildings and characteristics of land and buildings from 2005 to 2024. Geocoding was performed on the properties to identify them at the point level, and 82 properties were included in the analysis. Subsequently, landslide warning area polygons were obtained from the MLIT's National Land Numeric Data.

For this analysis, field surveys were conducted to collect attributes unavailable from open data. Specifically, the presence of stairs, road width, and road pavement were collected for all roads from the nearest station (Onomichi Station) to each property. It should be noted that the data cannot be released to the public due to privacy concerns, but portions can be made available upon request.

QGIS 3.34.1 was used for data integration. R 4.3.2 was also used in the analysis for the purpose of statistical analysis.

2.2 Method

A hedonic pricing model was used to identify factors affecting real estate prices. This model breaks down house prices into a set of attributes and estimates how much each attribute contributes to the price. For this analysis, we calculated the shortest network route from Onomichi Station to each property and extracted the road elements

along that route. Road typology was then used to enhance interpretability.

3 Result

First, the roads were classified into eight categories based on the presence of stairs, road width, and road pavement (Table 1). As a result, design paved road with stairs (Category 2) and Design paved alley (Category 6) were identified as area-specific streetscape elements. Even on flat land, asphalt paved alley (Category 3) was widely

Table 1. Classification and criteria of streetscapes

Category	Category name	Stairs	Pavement	Road width
1	Asphalt paved road with stairs	Yes	Asphalt	-
2	Design paved road with stairs	Yes	Stone, interlocking block, etc.	-
3	Asphalt paved alley	No	Asphalt	-2m
4	Asphalt paved narrow road	No	Asphalt	2-4m
5	Asphalt paved street	No	Asphalt	4m-
6	Design paved alley	No	Stone, interlocking block, etc.	-2m
7	Design paved narrow road	No	Stone, interlocking block, etc.	2-4m
8	Design paved street	No	Stone, interlocking block, etc.	4m-

distributed, which is inconvenient for automobile traffic (Figure 1).

Next, I estimated the parameters of a linear regression model that included road category and landslide warning zone. The results showed that categories 2 and 4 had a statistically significant negative correlation with real estate prices at the 5% significance level (Table 2). Conversely, properties located in a landslide warning zone did not have a statistically significant correlation with disaster risk.

4 Concluding Remarks

This study found a statistically significant negative correlation between roads representative of the local landscape and real estate prices. This is a reasonable result since such roads are located on steep slopes and are considered to be both inconvenient and correlated with disaster risk. In addition, real estate prices did not have a statistically significant correlation with disaster risk. This may be due to the fact that disaster risk was already factored into the road category, and this factor played a significant role.

However, several limitations exist in this study. First, the study was conducted in only a limited area of Onomichi,

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of classified streets

so the findings cannot be generalized. Further analysis should be conducted in the future to expand the area studied. Second, the road type categories used in this

Geographically Weighted Regression: Evidence from Amsterdam. *Tourism Management*, 91, 104523, 2022.

Table 2. Results of the linear regression model

Variable	Coef.	S.E.	p-value
<i>Real estate information</i>			
Land area	0.102	0.134	0.450
Dummy with existing house	-0.028	0.211	0.893
Road frontage width	0.362	0.108	0.001**
Dummy with stairs	-0.238	0.347	0.495
Distance to Onomichi station	-0.693	0.276	0.014*
Average slope from Onomichi station to property	-0.562	0.365	0.129
<i>Streetscape</i>			
View to the Inland Sea		—	
Road category 1	-0.132	0.390	0.736
Road category 2	-1.142	0.490	0.023*
Road category 3	0.180	0.307	0.561
Road category 4	-0.585	0.293	0.050*
Road category 6	0.265	0.430	0.539
Road category 7	-0.177	0.423	0.678
Road category 8	-0.137	0.399	0.732
<i>Disaster risk</i>			
Landslide warning zone	0.279	0.263	0.291
Sample size		82	
Adjusted R ²		0.293	
F-value		3.397***	
Max. VIF		4.860	

Note: Statistical significance ***0.1%, **1%, *5%, † 10%;
Coef.=Coefficient, S.E.=Standard Error; Continuous variables are logarithmized; The response variable is price per area.

analysis may correlate with livability and disaster risk; these correlations need to be identified. This will enable us to extract the inherent landscape value and discuss its impact on real estate prices.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The author declares that I have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing, improving grammar, and sentence structure, but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the author without AI assistance.

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